

Ductile-brittle fracture simulation of in-situ TiB₂/Al composite

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Introduction

SEM photography investigation on the in-situ TiB₂/2024 composite show that the sub-micro particles segregate along the grain boundaries to exhibit reticular distribution. The particle clusters were formed in the segregation region while some nano-particles were dispersively distributed inside the matrix. Therefore, suitable mesoscopic constitutive laws need to be developed. Representative volume element model should be built to study the mesoscopic fracture behavior and the effect of particles segregation degree.

Fig. 1: SEM images of TiB₂/2024 composite

Fracture mechanism

The in-situ tension tests were conducted via SEM. The brittle fracture of the particles agglomerations lead to the initiation of micro-cracks, the ductile fracture of the matrix area caused the coalescence of micro-cracks. The fracture behavior of the composites is ductile-brittle mixed mode fracture.

Fig. 2: Load-displacement curve

Fig. 3: Cracks within the particle segregation zones

Fig. 4: The coalescence of micro-cracks: (a) Local necking zone; (b) local fracture surface

Simulation

Two dimensional representative volume element (unit cell) models were established.

The von Mises yield criterion and the power hardening law were used to describe the nonlinear behavior of the matrix. The matrix failure was determined by Rice-Tracey local failure criterion.

Fig. 5: Hexagon-like segregation band of the 2D unit cell model

Fig. 6: the schematic of the unit cell model

Results and Discussion

- Simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental results of the uniaxial tension and in-situ tension.
- The increase of particle segregation degree leads to increased coefficient of variation of the maximum principal stress, so that the easier initiation of the micro cracks in particle segregation zone.
- higher level of particle segregation will accelerate the damage accumulation process, and further advance the ductile-brittle mixed fracture of composites.

Fig. 7: The engineering stress-strain curves from finite element simulations

Fig. 9: Mean value and standard deviation of the maximum stress vs. engineering strain

Fig. 10: Coefficient of variation of the maximum stress vs. engineering strain

Figure 8: Micro-crack initiation in the unit cells

Figure 12: The coalescence of micro-cracks in different unit cell models